

Взаимосвязь профессиональной идентичности с оценкой образовательной среды вуза студентами психологического направления обучения

Е. И. АРХИПОВА, В. А. КАПУСТИНА, М. А. МАТЮШИНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Активное и повсеместное внедрение цифровых инструментов обучения (массовые открытые онлайн-курсы, вебинары, блогинг и т. д.) привело к возникновению новых вопросов в отношении роли университета, в т. ч. в части формирования представлений студентов о себе и своем месте в профессиональном сообществе. Для студентов психологических профилей обучения крайне важно уметь грамотно выстраивать общение с другими людьми, что требует достаточно существенного самораскрытия на этапе профессиональной подготовки, но в условиях цифровой среды это довольно затруднительно, а эффективность очного формата тесно связана с восприятием пространства обучения как комфортного.

Цель нашего исследования – изучить оценку различных аспектов образовательной среды вуза студентами-психологами и выявить связи с их профессиональной идентичностью.

Материалы и методы. В опросе приняло участие 70 студентов Новосибирского государственного технического университета (Российская Федерация), обучающиеся по направлению «Психология», средний возраст – 19 лет. Использовались следующие опросники: опросник образовательной среды (В.А. Ясвин); опросник социально-психологической комфортности образовательной среды вуза (Г.Ю. Авдиенко); шкала оценки цифровой образовательной среды (М.Г. Сорокова и др.); методика исследования профессиональной идентичности (Л.Б. Шнейдер).

Результаты. У 90% студентов наблюдается непринятая идентичность с вузовской средой, у 80% наблюдаются признаки заниженной самооценки, связанной с деятельностью в вузе, у 63% наблюдается неудовлетворенная потребность в безопасности внутри вуза, у 58% наблюдается нестабильная профессиональная ориентация, связанная с образовательной средой, для 50% характерна неустойчивая мотивация к обучению. Студенты, чувствующие себя безопасно в образовательной среде вуза, оценивают образовательную среду вуза как более свободную ($R_s=0,48$; $p<0,05$) и творческую ($R_s=0,41$; $p<0,05$), а также не считают трудным освоение навыков практической деятельности в цифровой образовательной среде ($R_s=-0,57$; $p<0,01$) и не испытывают затруднений при планировании образовательной деятельности в ней ($R_s=-0,66$; $p<0,01$).

Заключение. Обнаружение корреляции между профессиональной идентичностью и восприятием цифровой образовательной среды у студентов-психологов свидетельствует о том, что среди специалистов-гуманитариев уровень недоверия к цифровым технологиям в образовании достаточно высок. Соответственно, цифровая образовательная среда вуза должна существенно измениться, чтобы использование цифровых инструментов в обучении ассоциировалось с качественным образованием. Выявление новых данных по оценке образовательной среды вуза предоставит возможности для разработки и внедрения социально-психологических практик сопровождения студентов в образовательном процессе.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

образовательная среда, профессиональное образование, студенты-психологи, профессиональная идентичность, цифровая образовательная среда, цифровое обучение

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

The relationship between professional identity and the assessment of the educational environment of the university by students majoring in psychology

E. I. ARKHIPOVA, V. A. KAPUSTINA, M. A. MATYUSHINA

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The active and widespread implementation of digital learning tools (massive open online courses, webinars, blogging, etc.) has led to the emergence of new questions regarding the role of the university, including in terms of forming students' self-concept and their place in the professional community. For students of psychological profiles of study, it is extremely important to be able to competently build communication with other people, which requires a significant self-disclosure at the stage of professional training. In the conditions of the digital environment, it is quite difficult, and the effectiveness of the face-to-face format is closely related to the perception of the learning space as comfortable.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted in the first half of 2023 by using Google forms. The sample included students at the Novosibirsk State Technical University studying in the field of Psychology (N=70), average age – 19 years. There were used the following questionnaires: Questionnaire of the educational environment by V.A. Yasvin; Questionnaire of social and psychological comfort of the educational environment by G. Yu. Avdienko; Digital educational environment rating scale; Questionnaire for studying professional identity by L.B. Shneider.

Results. 90% of students have an unaccepted identity with the university environment, 80% show signs of low self-esteem associated with activities at the university, 63% have an unsatisfied need for security within the university, 58% there is an unstable professional orientation associated with the educational environment, 50% are characterized by unstable motivation for learning. Students who feel safe in the educational environment of the university evaluate the educational environment of the university as freer ($R_s=0.48$, $p<0.05$) and creative ($R_s=0.41$, $p<0.05$), and also do not consider it difficult to acquire competencies in practical activities in digital educational environment ($R_s=-0.57$, $p<0.01$) and do not experience difficulties when planning educational activities in it ($R_s=-0.66$, $p<0.01$).

Conclusion. The discovery of a correlation between professional identity and the perception of the digital educational environment among psychology students suggests that among humanitarian specialists the level of mistrust in digital technologies in education is quite high. Accordingly, the digital educational environment of a university must change significantly for the use of digital tools in learning to be associated with quality education. Identification of new data on assessing the educational environment of a university will provide opportunities for the development and implementation of sociopsychological practices to accompany students in the educational process.

KEYWORDS

educational environment, professional education, psychology students, professional identity, digital educational environment, digital learning

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INTRODUCTION

As a part of the summit on transforming education, UN chief A. Guterres noted that "Education must be embraced by the digital revolution in the interests of all," and called for the development of high-quality digital educational content for all [1]. At the same time, the UNESCO report noted that the fastest pace of adoption of digital technologies is characteristic of higher education, while the prevalence of MOOCs and digital platforms "undermine the role of universities and create regulatory and ethical problems," including due to the presence of paid subscriptions and exclusive content [2].

The above allows us to talk about the relevance of studying the educational environment of university, especially in the context of its active digitalization. Creating an educational environment that contributes to the development of students' personal potential is one of the most important tasks of the education system. This helps students not only gain the knowledge and skills needed for a successful career, but also develop their individual abilities and talents. The educational environment of the university plays an important role in the formation of professional competencies and soft skills necessary for a successful career in psychology, which makes it possible to form a professional identity already as a student. Studying the educational environment and professional identity of students will identify factors and elements that contribute to successful student learning.

The purpose of our research is to study the assessment of various aspects and levels of the educational environment of a university by psychology students and to identify correlations with professional identity.

The literature review shows that educational environment acquired various interpretations:

- social cooperation, organizational cultures, virtual and physical environment that form students' experiences, cognition and studying [3].
- social system that involves the student, people surrounding him, conditions and aim of the interaction, terms and policies regulating this interaction. Sound learning environment is associated with professional development and high-quality learning [4].
- several elements of the learning environment are physical spaces, teaching approaches, social aspects, ICT and contextual learning places [5].

In the previous studies the focus was constraint to analyzing the physical characteristics of learning environment, now it is shifting to more profound understandings and perspectives [6; 7]. Psychosocial aspects of the learning environment are considered crucial for the student's outcomes. Students take center stage of the learning process, which require better understanding of their needs, expectations and experiences. This sensible approach to the learning process improvement was formulated in the "co-construction" idea of shared responsibility [8; 9].

The pedagogical aspect of learning environment comprises strategies, resources, methods, tools used to improve students' learning result [10].

Over time, an extensive literature has developed on analysis of existing assessment tools for measuring the educational systems efficacy. Noteworthy is the introduction of the National Higher Education Evaluation System in Brazil, which was considered a necessary and logical step towards the evaluation policies creation.

To a degree, the modifications made have attempted to align the state of the nation with the recommendations advanced in the report presented by the monitoring centre on borderless higher education. The emphasis is placed on the importance of knowledge for the advancement of a country, introducing reasonable improvements to higher education, lessening unequal competition between developing countries.

Another major aim is to promote the accessibility and better results of higher education, fighting the misperceptions of putting basic education at the forefront, diminishing the role of higher education [11].

The Brazilian National System for Higher Education Assessment is a developed system of higher education institutions regulation via diagnostics, regulatory and other types of assessments of their teaching and research. The program helps to assess various aspects, including social responsibility, student performance, university management, faculty, and facilities. This evaluation is carried out in three main components: assessment of higher education institutions, their courses, and student performance.

From the standpoint of the competence-based approach, in which the educational environment of the university is interpreted as a resource for the quality of professional training of specialists, we are talking about subject-subject relations.

The National Higher Education Assessment Committee (CONAES) oversees and manages the evaluation procedures, as mentioned by M.M. Polidori, C.M. Marinho-Araujo and G.B. Barreyro [12]. It focuses on formulating overall guidelines and directives for executing the evaluation system, while the operational responsibility falls on the National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira (INEP).

A group of researchers from the Moscow City Pedagogical University developed their own methodology for assessing the educational environment of a higher education institutions using different scales (SACERS, FCCERS, etc.). The technique allows to evaluate such qualities of the university environment as physical space, student interaction, digital environment and the structure of educational programs [13].

Moscow State University of Psychology and Education created the scale for assessing the digital educational environment of higher education institutions. The scale makes it possible to give a comprehensive characterization of the digital educational environment based on such indicators as compliance with the expectations about the educational process, stress tension, the need for support, satisfaction with communicative interaction, the use of dishonest strategies in controlling knowledge, accessibility [14].

The researchers considered various aspects of assessing the educational environments of universities in the context of digitalization; this experience and diagnostic tools are an important condition for the development of approaches to the digital educational environment assessing. There were attempts to assess the digital educational environment based on the ecopsychological approach, a method for the quality of the information and educational environment assessment based on the adapted system of self-review framework for information and communication technology. Thus, the criteria for assessing the digital educational environment are: consistency, mobility, openness, informality, completeness, freedom, accessibility, security. Despite of the several aspects analysis, the approach itself is still not completely developed [15].

The variety of definitions of the concept of "digital educational environment", which exists in the pedagogical literature, is due to the semantic accents made by the authors when determining the structure of the environment. So, the emphasis is placed on technical solutions to support educational, methodological and information activities. The digital educational atmosphere is perceived as a set of interconnected elements in educational activities, enabled by digital technologies and educational resources, that provide subjects with opportunities to learn about culture, self-actualization, and social behavior.

Thus, the broad scope of the learning process details consideration can contribute to the development of effective educational environment assessment tools.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research methods: analysis of scientific literature, psychological testing, methods of mathematical data processing (correlation analysis, comparative analysis).

The study includes the following questionnaires, for assessing the educational environment:

- Questionnaire of the educational environment by V.A. Yasvin [16];
- Questionnaire of social and psychological comfort of the educational environment by G. Yu. Avdienko [17];
- Digital educational environment rating scale [14];

For assessing the professional identity:

- Questionnaire for studying professional identity by L.B. Shneider [18].

When carrying out the questionnaire of V.A. Yasvin, we asked students to answer questions separately about the university and the department in which they study, which allowed us to take a more differentiated look at the different levels of the educational environment of the university.

The sample included students at the Novosibirsk State Technical University studying in the field of Psychology (37.03.01), in the amount of 70 people, average age 19 years.

The study was conducted in the first half of 2023 by using Google Forms (<https://forms.gle/aB6PJoPpSTV7gLSU6>).

All students who took part in the study were informed about its purpose and expressed their readiness to cooperate and participate in it.

RESULTS

The results of applying descriptive and quantitative statistics are presented below.

Picture 1 Average values according to the digital educational environment rating scale

Analysis of the assessment of the digital environment of the university showed that all average values are within the normal range at the lower limits, except Dishonest strategies (Picture 1).

Analysis of an integral indicator of satisfaction with the educational process in the digital environment showed the result lower than normal. It could be explained by consequences of implementation of the digital education in a period of COVID-19, when most teachers and students were not ready to work in a digital environment.

Picture 2 Average values according to the digital educational environment rating scale (integral indicator)

Picture 3 Average values according to the questionnaire of social and psychological comfort of the educational environment by G. Yu. Avdienko

Analysis of the results of the questionnaire «Sociopsychological comfort of the educational environment» showed that the majority of students rate the sociopsychological comfort of the educational environment very low on all scales. It could affect the quality of the educational process, mastery of skills and competencies and cause difficulties in the process of forming a professional identity.

Picture 4 Percentage distribution of professional identity (PI) assessment results

Studying the professional identity of psychology students (Questionnaire by L.B. Shneider). 44% (31 students) – diffuse professional identity; 33% (23 students) – moratorium on professional identity; 13% (9 students) – premature professional identity; 6% (4 students) – achieved professional identity; 4% (3 students) – pseudo-identity. Most students (44%) have a diffuse professional identity as a characteristic, indicating that the professional choice is not made definitively, and students have a weak representation of their professional future. A third of student are characterized by a moratorium on professional identity. Such students are typically worried about how to build professional trajectory within the chosen direction.

To study the relationships between parameters for assessing the educational environment, we used the Spearman test.

Table 1

Results of study the correlations between parameters for assessing the educational environment

	Need for support in educational activities in the educational center	Activity (university) parameter	Freedom parameter	Competencies in practical activities in the digital educational environment	Planning educational activities in the digital educational environment
Degree of satisfaction of security needs		$R_s=0.41, p\leq 0.05$	$R_s=0.48, p\leq 0.05$	$R_s=-0.57, p\leq 0.05$	$R_s=-0.66, p\leq 0.01$
Self-esteem	$R_s=-0.51, p\leq 0.05$	$R_s=0.35, p\leq 0.05$	-	-	-
Identity with the university environment	$R_s=-0.62, p\leq 0.01$	$R_s=0.34, p\leq 0.05$	-	-	-

The greatest number of correlations in the parameter “Degree of satisfaction of security needs” was found (Table 1). Students who feel safe in the educational environment of the university and do not feel the need to defend themselves from anyone assess the educational environment of the university as a whole as freer ($R_s=0.48, p\leq 0.05$) and active ($R_s=0.41, p\leq 0.05$), and also do not assess the acquisition of competencies in practical activities in the digital educational environment as difficulties ($R_s=-0.57, p\leq 0.05$) and do not experience difficulties when planning educational activities in the digital educational environment ($R_s=-0.66, p\leq 0.01$).

Negative correlations were found between the parameters Need for support in educational activities in the educational center and Self-esteem ($R_s=-0.51, p\leq 0.05$) and the Need for support in educational activities in the educational center and Identity with the university environment ($R_s=-0.62, p\leq 0.01$). It could indicate that students who are satisfied with the results of their activities experience fewer difficulties when planning time for classes, when assessing technical difficulties, and they perceive the electronic learning format as more familiar.

It is possible to note the positive correlations between the Activity (university) parameter according to the methodology of V.A. Yasvin with such parameters as Identity with the university environment ($R_s=0.34, p\leq 0.05$) and Self-esteem ($R_s=0.35, p\leq 0.05$). Students who are satisfied with the results of their activities, feel a sense of security in the educational environment, feel like a representative of this university. It is typical for them to evaluate the educational environment of the university as more active.

Negative correlations were found between parameters for assessing the digital educational environment and the professional identity of psychology students (Table 2), namely Professional Identity & Satisfaction with the educational process in the digital educational environment ($R_s=-0.75, p\leq 0.001$), Professional Identity & Satisfaction with communicative interaction and motivation to study in the digital educational environment ($R_s=-0.74, p\leq 0.001$). Students with

positive professional identity statuses assess digital educational environment as a less suitable environment for professional development, preferring the full-time format of education. Such students have a weak need for support for their activities in the digital educational environment and do not seek to use deceptive strategies in the learning process (Professional Identity & Need for support in educational activities in the digital educational environment ($R_s = -0.75$, $p \leq 0.001$), Professional Identity & Dishonest strategies in the digital education environment ($R_s = -0.75$, $p \leq 0.001$)).

Table 2

Results of study the relationships between parameters for assessing the professional identity

Parameters	R_s -meaning	p-level
Professional Identity & Satisfaction with the educational process in the digital educational environment	-0.75	0.001
Professional Identity & Satisfaction with communicative interaction and motivation to study in the digital educational environment	-0.74	0.001
Professional Identity & Need for support in educational activities in the digital educational environment	-0.75	0.001
Professional Identity & Dishonest strategies in the digital education environment	-0.75	0.001

DISCUSSION

The data we obtained about the negative correlation between professional identity and the digital environment are similar with the data of S. Kwon. S. Kwon et al. note that the active adoption of online learning should promote identity changes for both teachers and students, but such changes were rare in their study [19]. In fact, for the digital educational environment to become the basis for a new pedagogical culture of courses, it is important not only to increase the technical and digital literacy of participants in the educational process, but to intensify the communicative component of learning.

Scientists from China came to similar conclusions about the relation between identity and the educational environment. X. Liu et. al. found the positive correlation between professional identity of Chinese students and their career adaptability and recommended to do a «conducive academic environment and more opportunities for career practice» at colleges [20].

The result of a correlation between self-esteem and the need for support in the digital educational environment has similarities with results of M. Gellisch et. al.: a positive correlation between self-efficacy and enjoyment, as well as a negative correlation with anxiety, was found in first-year medical students in both face-to-face learning and active or passive online learning [21].

The need for support in the digital educational environment, probably, is an indicator of a lack of interaction with teachers, which is consistent with the results of L. Andryukhina et al., who found that most Russian teachers consider the digital educational environment as an object of observation and analysis, but do not seek to involve students into online learning in an active format [22]. For example, to engage students in the digital educational space, it is possible to use such distance learning technologies as web quests, online challenges, online marathons, mobile applications, artificial neural network, etc. [23]. Scientists from Ecuador and Spain also note that the use of game elements in learning (rewards, tasks and competitions) makes learning more attractive for students, because this creates an interactive and relevant educational environment [24]. However, when organizing communication in the educational process, it is important for teachers to competently manage the online educational interactive environment, which can arise because of multilateral discussions regarding duplication and "clutter" in the dialogue [25].

CONCLUSION

The study found that most students have an unaccepted identity with the university, a low self-esteem associated with the university environment and an unmet need for security.

Students with positive professional identity statuses evaluate the digital educational environment as a less suitable environment for professional development, preferring the full-time format of education. Students who feel safe in the educational environment of the university evaluate the educational environment of the university as freer and more creative, and do not consider it difficult to acquire competencies in practical activities in digital educational environment and do not experience difficulties when planning educational activities.

The prospects of the study are related to the study of the assessment of the educational environment of the university by students of other areas of training, as well as the study of the relationship between the assessment of the educational environment of the university and such constructs as professional identity and professional resilience.

Identification of new data on assessing the educational environment of a university will provide opportunities for the development and implementation of sociopsychological practices to accompany students in the educational process.

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Авторы**Архипова Елена Ивановна**

(Россия, Новосибирск)

Кандидат филологических наук, доцент кафедры
иностраных языков гуманитарного факультета
Новосибирский государственный технический университет

E-mail: e.arhipova@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9992-3443

Scopus Author ID: 57206856111

Капустина Валерия Анатольевна

(Россия, Новосибирск)

Кандидат психологических наук, доцент, заведующий
кафедрой психологии и педагогики
Новосибирский государственный технический университет

E-mail: kapustina@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-8872-0306

Scopus Author ID: 57210418116

Матюшина Марина Александровна

(Россия, Новосибирск)

Старший преподаватель кафедры психологии и педагогики
Новосибирский государственный технический университет

E-mail: m.a.matyushina@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0957-6631

Authors**Elena I. Arkhipova**

(Russia, Novosibirsk)

Cand. Sci. (Philol.), Associate Professor of the Department of
Foreign Languages, Faculty of Humanities
Novosibirsk State Technical University

E-mail: e.arhipova@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0001-9992-3443

Scopus Author ID: 57206856111

Valeria A. Kapustina

(Russia, Novosibirsk)

Cand. Sci. (Psychol.), Associate Professor, Head of the
Department of Psychology and Pedagogy
Novosibirsk State Technical University

E-mail: kapustina@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-8872-0306

Scopus Author ID: 57210418116

Marina A. Matyushina

(Russia, Novosibirsk)

Senior Lecturer, Department of Psychology and Pedagogy
Novosibirsk State Technical University

E-mail: m.a.matyushina@corp.nstu.ru

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0957-6631

Вклад авторов

Архипова Е. И.: концептуализация, методология,
руководство исследованием, администрирование
данных, создание рукописи и её редактирование

Капустина В. А.: администрирование данных,
создание черновика рукописи

Матюшина М. А.: визуализация, формальный
анализ, создание рукописи и её редактирование

Author's contribution

Elena I. Arkhipova: Conceptualization, Methodology,
Supervision, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing
Valeria A. Kapustina: Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft
Marina A. Matyushina: Visualization, Formal analysis,
Writing - Review & Editing

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